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The discovery of active sulfide-depositing hydrothermal vents on oceanic spreading centers has led to renewed interest in the magmatic plumbing systems that drive hydrothermal systems. A number of approaches have been used to evaluate sub-axial magmatic plumbing systems including 1) analyses of heat flow, 2) determination of ridge structure using seismic refraction and multi-channel reflection techniques, 3) petrologic studies of the erupted lavas to determine the extent of differentiation and mixing the magmas underwent prior to eruption, and 4) photogeologic interpretation of the axis to decipher the volcanic and tectonic history of selected segments of the ridge. The last approach has benefitted greatly from comparative studies on subaerial volcanoes and is the topic of this paper. Although, submarine and subaerial volcanoes differ in some respects, they are similar in many others. Recent studies of subaerial volcanoes have focussed on eruption patterns. The frequency, sizes and locations of eruptions provide clues to the location, size, and state of the magma sources and the plumbing systems that deliver magma to the surface. Eruption patterns can also show how magma systems respond to perturbation arising from tectonism and other processes. It is our aim here to show how eruption patterns can be used to study the volcanism along submarine rift zones. Our discussion is based on analogies with subaerial volcanoes.

In order to study eruption patterns, we need first a history of eruptions. For volcanoes where an eyewitness record is not available, this history must be constructed from geologic mapping of the eruption products and determination of their age. It is helpful if we can classify the eruption products in a way that distinguishes the behavior of one eruption from another. This type of geologic analysis can be illustrated using Kilauea volcano, a well-studied subaerial volcano in Hawaii.

Kilauea a rifted subaerial volcano. Kilauea is the youngest of five large shield volcanoes comprising the island of Hawaii (Figure 1). The emerged part of Kilauea is the top of a broad, dome-like ridge rising more than 6 km from the ocean floor and about 1200 m above sea level. Although eyewitness accounts of eruptions at Kilauea go back only 200 years, the volcano has had a long history of frequent eruptions.

Recent mapping has shown that 70% of Kilauea's subaerial surface is younger than 500 years, 90% younger than 1000 years (Figure 2A). Although the frequency and volume of eruptions have remained roughly constant on the volcano as a whole through its life, the locus of activity has shifted in response to structural changes in the volcanic edifice.

The surface of Kilauea is broken by many fractures (Figure 2B), which define five structural regions (Figure 2C): a summit plateau indented by a caldera, two rift zones extending away from the caldera and along the axis of the volcanic ridge, an unfractured north flank buttressed by Kilauea's neighbor Mauna Loa, and a free south flank that is moving seaward. The rift zones owe their origin to gravitational spreading of the ridge (Fiske and Jackson, 1972). The movement of the free flank is probably facilitated by sliding of the volcanic edifice over an underlying layer of deep-sea sediments (Nakamura, 1982).

The summit region has undergone repeated intervals of caldera collapse and filling. The most

Figure 1. Map of Hawaii showing the five volcanoes that make up the island. The heavy stippling shows the subaerial rift zones of Kilauea and Mauna Loa volcanoes. The submarine portion of the Kilauea east rift is the pronounced ridge extending more than 50 km to the northeast from the easternmost tip of Hawaii. Figure from Fiske and Jackson (1972).

recent large collapses occurred about 200 and 1500 years ago (Holcomb, 1981). Each time explosive eruptions followed and produced extensive sheets of pyroclastic material. Similar pyroclastic layers exposed in the fault scarps of the south flank suggest that many more collapses have occurred within roughly the past 40,000 years (Easton, 1978).

The rift zones are covered by lava flows of various ages (Figure 3). The older flows are broken rift structures, and dating of the lavas has shown that both rifting and eruptions are episodic. When short segments of the rift zone are considered individually, the timing of the episodes has no particular significance, but when examined collectively the episodes form patterns of activity migrating along the rift zones.

These patterns are accentuated when the eruptions are classified according to differences in behavior and eruptive products. A behavioral feature of an eruption that is easily classified is its duration; eruptions differing in duration produce lava flows differing in surface morphology. Brief eruptions produce unchanneled pahoehoe near their vents and aa farther away. Eruptions of longer duration produce highly channelized lava flows fed by lava tubes. Mapping of these different flow types over Kilauea shows that different parts of the volcano experience different kinds of eruptions, and that any one area has different kinds of eruptions at different times.

In general, eruptions are long-lived near the summit and brief near the far ends of the rift zones. Between these extremes, along the middle and upper segments of the rifts, eruptions are either brief or sustained; characteristically an interval of long quiescence is broken by a flurry of brief eruptions and then by sustained activity. Intervals of long and stable eruption at the summit are accompanied by dormancy along the rift zones, and summit activity wanes when the rift zones become active.

The eruptive activity is roughly cyclical,

Figure 2. A. Map of Kilauea volcano subdividing the surficial lava flows by age. B. Map of Kilauea volcano showing eruptive and non-eruptive fissures, craters, and faults. C. Map of Kilauea volcano showing the five major structural regions of the volcano: the north and south flanks, the summit, and the east and southwest rift zones. Figures from Holcomb (1981).

migrating back and forth between the summit and rift zones over intervals of decades and centuries. It also appears to be synchronized with structural developments such as caldera collapse and slumping movement of the unbuttressed south flank.

These gradual changes in behavior are illustrated by Kilauea's eruptions during the past 400 years (Holcomb, 1981). At the beginning of this interval, summit activity had been dominant for a long time, such that the caldera had been filled and buried beneath a cluster of lava shields. During the 1700's, however, this summit activity waned, and eruptions became frequent along the rift zones. Early in that century, following the last sustained eruption at the summit, Kilauea's east rift zone was re-broken and

Figure 3. Detailed map of about 7 km of the middle east rift zone of Kilauea showing fissures covered by younger flows and other flows cut by younger fissures. These field relations demonstrate that both rifting and eruption are episodic. Figure from Holcomb (1981).

dilated by an episode of rifting. The eruptions that followed from the east rift zone were brief at first, but in about AD1750 a sustained eruption occurred from a vent at low elevation along the lower subaerial segment of the rift zone. Other eruptions followed, including an especially large series at low elevation in about AD 1790. Then in 1790 a large explosive eruption associated with summit collapse deposited a thick layer of tephra around the rejuvenated caldera. There followed a century of continuous eruption within the caldera but hardly any activity at all along the rift zones. In 1924 the pattern changed again after minor collapse and explosions at the summit that apparently followed a submarine eruption. Since that time, summit eruptions have been relatively infrequent and brief. East rift eruptions have increased in frequency since 1955, and one eruption from the upper part of the rift zone continued with little interruption for nearly six years. An episode of flank slumping in 1975 was followed by a short interval of dormancy, but the eruption frequency has increased again and may be leading to another interval of sustained activity, this time along the middle part of the subaerial east rift zone.

The frequency and duration of eruptions are

thought to depend upon the amount of magma stored at shallow levels and the degree of continuity existing within the plumbing system. If there is little magma and the reservoirs are poorly connected, the eruptions will be infrequent and brief. But if there is much magma in well-connected reservoirs, the eruptions will be frequent and sustained. Long-term changes in eruptive behavior therefore reflect changes in the volcano's plumbing system.

Kilauea's plumbing system transports magma both vertically and horizontally to the summit and rift zones. Most vertical transport occurs beneath the summit where a deep conduit brings magma up from at least the lower lithosphere into a shallow reservoir system within the volcano. From this reservoir system, the shallow plumbing distributes the magma to the summit and rift zones. The path taken by a batch of magma depends upon the hydrostatic pressure and friction existing within different parts of the plumbing system. Evolution of the plumbing system may explain long-term eruptive changes. Figure 4

Figure 4. A model of the magmatic plumbing system to explain the changes in eruptive patterns through time and space. Model is discussed in text. Kilauea is presently in the third phase with infrequent summit eruptions and sustained rift eruptions. Figure from Holcolm (1981).

illustrates one evolutionary model based on repeated collapse and filling of the summit caldera. A similar model could be based on recurrent slippage of the mobile south flank and spreading of the rift zones. The relationship between caldera collapse and flank slumping remains uncertain. It is important that eruption patterns of subaerial volcanoes change, probably in response to changes in the magmatic plumbing system and that the plumbing system can be understood through study of the surficial lava flows. A similar approach can be used to study submarine volcanoes and volcanic rifts such as oceanic spreading centers.

The Galapagos submarine rift zone. Recent studies show that submarine rift zones are in some ways similar to Kilauea. An example is a segment of the Galapagos rift (Figure 5). The rift is similar in width and inferred depth to its shallow magma reservoir to Kilauea. Volcanism is episodic, such that lava flows of three or more distinctly different ages can be found at most localities along it. Dilation appears to be episodic. Lava flows are basaltic and similar morphologically to the lava of Kilauea. Moreover, the morphology of the lava flows is variable in a way that appears to be analogous to subaerial lava flows: "sheet flows" are poorly channelized and probably are products of brief eruptions; "pillowed flows" are highly channelized and probably result from sustained eruptions. Sheet flows and pillowed flows tend to dominate different segments of the rift at different times.

These similarities to Kilauea suggest that submarine magma plumbing system can be analyzed in terms of eruption patterns using the morphology of lava flows in a manner analogous to that used for Kilauea. Sporadic brief eruptions probably indicate poorly developed plumbing systems, and sustained eruptions, well-developed plumbing systems. Long-term changes in eruptive behavior indicate that these plumbing systems evolve through time and space just like that of Kilauea.

It should be added, however, that the subaerial and submarine rifts may not be similar in all respects. Figure 4 is an illustration of the general kinds of changes that may occur; the actual changes may be very different. Calderas, for example, may not be present along the submarine rifts, and little lateral transport may occur within their plumbing systems. Nevertheless, the existence of such eruption patterns points to the occurrence of interpretable processes occurring within the plumbing systems. An understanding of those processes should be of great value in the study of submarine hydrothermal systems. Detailed study of submarine patterns

The similarity of subaerial rifts like Kilauea to submarine rifts like the Galapagos rift suggests that both should be amenable to the same type of study. We have little doubt that a great deal will be learned about submarine rifts using methods applied to Kilauea. This work will require three different activities: 1) dating of flows, 2) mapping flow morphology, and 3) refining our understanding of submarine flow morphology.

The most promising method to accurately and precisely determine the ages of lava flows is the paleomagnetic method based on the secular variation of the earth's magnetic field. Reliable histories of secular variation either exist or will be available in the near future for several areas of particular interest including Hawaii, the Galapagos, Mexico, and the Pacific Northwest. The barrier to using this method is technological. We currently have no way of collecting precisely oriented rock samples in the submarine environment. It is essential that 6 to 15 samples be collected from each site on a given lava flow, each core oriented to within an accuracy of one

Figure 5. Geologic map of a section of the Galapagos rift near 86°W. Flows are divided into three age groups based on sediment cover and into two morphologic groups. Note that different parts of the rift are dominated by flows of different age and morphology. These variations probably reflect variations in the underlying magmatic plumbing system. Figure from Ballard and others (1979).

degree. Assuming that gycoscopic orientations can achieve this accuracy, the detachment and recovery of samples is still problematic.

Classification and mapping the distribution of submarine lava flows relies mainly on deep-toward camera systems. Manned submersibles are of comparatively little use except for detailed study of critical localities or novel phenomena. The towed camera systems should cover large tracts; realtime video would assist in optimizing the tractlines of the camera sled.

Our understanding of submarine lava flow morphology is still somewhat inadequate. For example, the formation of pillow lava is not well understood.

Though in general pillowed flows appear to be analogous to highly channelized tube-fed pahoehoe, pillows also occur in other situations such as along the stagnating margins of sheet flows and along fissure vents as the eruptions wane. Evidently the occurrence of pillows is not restricted to the distal ends of long distributary lava-tube systems. We must learn to recognize the pillows formed in different settings so that we can correctly interpret the eruptive behavior. We have more to learn about the ponding and subsidence of submarine lava lakes, the transition from sheet flows to rough-surfaced flows (probably analogous to the transition of subaerial pahoehoe to aa), and the submarine eruptive fissures. No open eruptive fissures have been observed in the submarine environment. Problems such as these will require careful detailed studies of selected sites in addition to the broader-scale camera surveys.

A suggested strategy

We suggest a detailed study of Kilauea's submarine east rift zone to learn more about the interpretation of submarine lava-flow morphology. This rift should be roughly similar in structure and lava-flow morphology to those of submarine spreading centers, however, it has the advantage that its volcanic history is already well constrained by that of the subaerial segment. For example, we know that magma is transported laterally into the submarine portion of the rift. We can also infer when the submarine rift was dormant and when the most recent large submarine eruptions occurred from the history of summit collapses. We can infer the volumes and the rough duration of past submarine eruptions and can use this knowledge to study the nature of the submarine lava flows. At Kilauea we have the opportunity to concentrate on problems of lava flow morphologic

interpretation where the plumbing system of the rift-zone is well constrained. Once we have used Kilauea to establish a more detailed morphologic interpretation, we can apply this knowledge to delineate the eruption patterns of submarine rift zones at oceanic spreading centers. The eruption pattern along spreading centers can then be used to evaluate the sub-axial magmatic plumbing systems and their associated hydrothermal circulation systems.

REFERENCES

- Ballard, R.D., Holcolm, R.T., and Van Andel, T.H., 1979, The Galapagos Rift at 86°W: Sheet flows, collapse pits, and lava lakes of the Rift Valley. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 84, p. 5407-5422.
- Easton, E.M., 1978, Stratigraphy and petrology of the Hilini Formation: The oldest exposed lavas of Kilauea volcano. Unpub. M.Sc. Thesis, University of Hawaii at Manoa, Honolulu, Hawaii, 274 p.
- Fiske, R.S., and Jackson, E.D., 1972, Orientation and growth of Hawaiian volcanic rifts: the effect of regional structure and gravitational stresses. *Proc. R. Soc. Lond. A.* 329, p. 299-326.
- Holcolm, R.T., 1981, The Kilauea Volcano, Hawaii; Chronology and morphology of the surficial lava flows. Unpublished Ph.D. dissertation, Stanford University, 321 p.
- Nakamura, T., 1982, Why do long rift zones develop better in Hawaiian volcanoes - a possible role of thick oceanic sediments. *Univesidade dos acores, Ponta del Gato, Symposium on activity of oceanic volcanoes*, p. 59-73.